

Factors Influence Employees' Work Engagement: Literature Review

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Abstract:

The paper aims to measure work engagement and look at the areas where management interventions can be implemented to increase the overall level of employee engagement drafting several solution and recommendation for locality in Bac Ninh to attract and maintain more high qualified middle managers within FDI enterprises.

Keywords: Work engagement, FDI enterprises.

1. Introduction

Work engagement is a common concept, both in the business context and in the academy. This term first appeared in the 1990s and meanwhile, more than 200 scientific publications have appeared on this topic. According to a global survey of CEOs, attracting employees is one of the five most important challenges for organizations. Consequently, international business consulting firms have developed their own proprietary concepts and survey tools. Based on large international databases, covering many different industries, these companies estimate that only about 20% of all employees are involved in their jobs, while another 20% be relaxed and about 60% participate in moderation. These consulting companies also state that employee engagement promotes business success (Schaufeli) 2012. It is concluded that work engagement is a feasible concept for both science and practice and it needs to be paid more attention and applied to the operational practices of businesses.

FDI inflows are a very important driving force for Vietnam's economic development and have a large contribution to Vietnam's GDP growth. In particular, Bac Ninh province with good FDI attraction and one of the localities with the most FDI enterprises in the country.

With the advantage of being located in the Northern key economic region, in recent years, Bac Ninh province has become a destination for many foreign investors with more than 1,000 foreign direct investment (FDI) projects. By the end of June 2029, the total registered foreign investment capital in Bac Ninh province reached nearly 17 billion USD (Nhandan), 2019.

On the other hand, in these enterprises, the middle management staff is mainly Vietnamese and plays a backbone for the activities of FDI enterprises. The work engagement of these managers to businesses is one of the important development drivers of enterprises in general and FDI enterprises in Bac Ninh in particular.

According to Gallup Report (2019), companies with a team attached to the job will increase the competitive advantage by 202%. Therefore, the research topic: "An analysis on the work engagement of Vietnamese middle managers: the case of FDI enterprises - Bac Ninh province" is very urgent and suitable with practical needs in order to offer advanced solutions for work engagement of management at FDI enterprises in Vietnam (SKHDT BN), 2019.

Thus, in theory, work engagement in human resource management is also a very important term and is mentioned by many domestic and foreign studies. In terms of Vietnam's economy, FDI enterprises are the main development drivers and Bac Ninh province is the most typical province in terms of FDI attraction as well as reasonable support mechanisms for FDI enterprises. On the enterprise level, middle managers are the core force and the bridge between Vietnamese workers and foreign leaders.

2. Literature review

2.1. Foreigner studies on employees work engagement

- The research of Hersey & Blanchard (2001), "The Labor Relations Institutes of New York" built for the first time applied to workers in the industry, with 9 encouraging components for employees, including:

Autonomy at work: The employee has control and responsibility for his work, is encouraged to participate in work-related decisions and is encouraged to take initiatives.

Interesting work: Expressing through the diversity, creativity and challenges of the job and the opportunity to use the individual's abilities.

Fully recognized work done: Recognized when completing the work well, as well as contributing to the success of the company.

High salary: Receive a salary that is commensurate with the results of work and ensures a sufficient personal life

Long-term work: Having a stable job, no need to worry about how to keep a job or look for new jobs.

Good working conditions: Related issues such as labor safety, hygiene, environment, working time, etc. are above average in the industry.

Career advancement and development: Individuals always have opportunities for advancement and development in the organization.

Support from superiors: The superiors always show their care and support in solving labor problems.

- According to Vishwanath V. Baba and Muahammad Jamal (1979) with the topic "On Becker's Theory of Commitment: An Empirical Verification among Blue-Collar Workers", through a survey of 377 production workers in 6 companies in the city. Vancouver, the author has pointed out that the three factors that influence workers' engagement with the organization are (1) Demographics, (2) Background, and (3) Job factors. In which, job factors include: variety of jobs; relaxing time; the help of colleagues; the convenience of going to the office, which is considered the main factors determining the work engagement and attitude of employees to the organization and the work.

- W. D. Kahn (1990) with study "Psychological Conditions of Personal Engagement and Disengagement at Work", is credited with conceptualizing the major components of employee engagement. His model proposes that engagement differs from basic job involvement, in that it focuses not on worker skills but, rather, on how one commits him/herself during the performance of the job. Engagement entails the active use of emotions in addition to the simple use of cognition while completing work tasks. The major propositions of the model are that people express themselves cognitively, physically, and emotionally while performing their work roles. The model proposes that, in order for individuals to fully engage with their job, three psychological conditions must be met in the work environment: meaningfulness safety, and availability

- The study of Coffman and Gonzalez-Molina (2002), "How the world's greatest organizations drive growth by unleashing human potential" Employee engagement is also something that is changeable, and can vary widely from one workplace to another Studies indicate that workers are, to some extent, a reflection of the administrators of an agency. Low or conversely high engagement scores have been traced back to the organization's leadership, from top to bottom. Therefore, the results of engagement studies should have considerable applicability to the social work field. For instance, leaders in human service agencies could utilize data from engagement studies to create and implement strategies that would increase staff engagement

- The study of May, Gilson, and Harter (2004), "The psychological conditions of meaningfulness, safety and availability and the engagement of the human spirit at work" conducted a field study in a large Midwestern insurance agency. Using a survey format they explored why some individuals fully engage in their work while others become alienated or completely disengaged. Results of this study confirmed that engagement differs from simple job satisfaction. They agreed that engagement actually entails the active use of emotions and behaviors in addition to cognitions. Overall, study results supported Kahn's earlier work in that psychological meaningfulness and safety were positively linked to employee investment in work roles. Additionally, job enrichment and role fit were positively related to psychological meaningfulness. Having a supportive supervisor and good relations with co-workers were related to feelings of psychological safety on the job.

- Harter, Schmidt, and Hayes (2002), "Business-unit-level employee satisfaction, employee engagement, and business outcome analysis" completed a meta-analysis of prior studies on employee engagement that were conducted by the Gallup Organization. The researchers examined the relationship between employee satisfaction- engagement, and the business-unit outcomes of customer satisfaction, productivity, profit, employee turnover, and accidents. Harter et al. (2002) noted that one of the defining elements of employee engagement is the actionable quality of the measured concepts. In other words, employee engagement is related to meaningful business outcomes and many of the core issues of engagement are ones over which managers can have substantial influence. High levels of satisfaction and employee engagement were positively correlated with customer satisfaction, profitability, productivity, and safety outcomes.

- A study of Schaufeli, Bakker, and Salanova (2006), "The measurement of engagement with a short questionnaire: A cross-national study" surveyed 14,521 employees in various occupations, using a self-report questionnaire that measured work engagement. The researchers found that engagement is not only the opposite of burnout but that it has its own characteristics, which were labeled vigor, dedication, and absorption. The researchers concluded that engagement is similar to burnout in that it is a stable, non-transient state that increases slightly with age. Additionally, blue collar workers were less engaged than managers, educators, and police officers. Engagement did not seem to differ systematically between genders.

Although there are many studies related to work engagement in many organizations with many different research methods, there has not been any research focused on middle management group and in FDI enterprises in Bac Ninh. Accordingly, the middle management team in these enterprises is mainly Vietnamese while the senior management is foreigners.

2.2. Classification of work engagement

With regard to work engagement, employees can be divided into 3 groups. According to Williams and Schneiderman (2002), there are three types of people: (1) Engaged employees, (2) Not engaged employees, and (3) Actively disengaged employees.

- (1) Engaged employees: Group of employees who are not attached to the work (engaged employees). Those who tend to focus on specific tasks rather than the goals and expected results in their roles. Employees who are not associated with the organization do not have a good relationship with their management and colleagues, because they tend to feel their contribution is ignored and their potential is not known. They want advice, specific guidance on what needs to be done, and focus on completing specific tasks (Gallup, 2004).

- (2) Not engaged employees: Group of employees associated with the work (not engaged employees). These are people with a constructive spirit. They want to know the expected outcome in their role so that they can achieve and reap the results beyond that expectation. They naturally care about the company and their role in the company. Their performance is always high, working with passion. And they want to use their talents and strengths in their daily work and towards innovation to help their organizations grow (Gallup, 2004).

- (3) Actively disengaged employees: The group of proactive employees who are not associated with the work. Those who are "separatist" and almost resolutely against everything. They not only do not feel happy at work, but also always express their unhappy attitude. Every day, this group of people seeks to undermine the success of colleagues associated with the job (Gallup, 2004).

Humphrey et al. (2007) suggest that contextual features should be conceptually integrated into a job specification model because they represent a class of job characteristics focused on the following factors context of the work. Moreover, Kahn (1990) argues that because of material needs and working conditions, workers perform tasks as if guided by external scenarios, instead of investing themselves in their jobs. , so they are likely to be negatively involved. As physical demands and stressful working conditions increase, workers will become physically uncomfortable, leading to more negative experiences while working.

2.3. The importance of work engagement on FDI enterprises.

Firstly, work engagement as Balogun and Johnson (2005) is as a factor affecting the results and performance of the business: Employees are the decisive factor to the performance of each department as well as the performance of the whole enterprise. Employees with high professional skills, problem solving skills and creative dynamics will help improve the performance of the business.

Therefore, if the employee is assigned with a suitable job as well as creating favorable conditions to perform work effectively, improve work engagement, businesses will get positive results.

Secondly, work engagement is as a factor to ensure business secrets - essential conditions for the success of the business (Williams and Schneiderman, 2002) When an employee leaves, the business not only loses part of the necessary knowledge and skills they have accumulated while working but also help other businesses get those elements without training, investing time and cost. If the person who is quitting is a senior manager who holds many business secrets, business strategies, social relationships as well as business relationships with partners or engineers who hold real technology secrets export to work for competitors of the business, so the loss will be the greater.

Thirdly, work engagement is as a basis for resources for sustainable development: Human resources play an important role in the knowledge economy, they capture knowledge and skills as well as important relationships of businesses and determine the development strategy of the enterprise, which is the base resource for leaders to develop development strategies. The development strategy of any business must be based on its available resources both financially and personnel El- Kot et al. (2010). The presence and cohesion of the workforce will be an important factor for the implementation and adjustment process, which is the basis for making longer-term strategies and higher development goals.

Fourth, work engagement is as the basis for the formation of ideas for development: In the current information age, the stage of developing global knowledge economy, the source of knowledge and information is what determines competitive advantage. Good and associate employees are the key force to ensure and improve the enterprise's advantages. They are also the main force for ideas and creativity in the production, the quality of goods and services of the business, improve the process, make the difference with competitors.

Finally, work engagement is as a valuable asset of the enterprise: Finding, recruiting, and mobilizing new employees to grasp the job, having the ability to run the operations of companies is a time-consuming and costly process. . The company has to pay for new hiring, training and probation and it takes a long time to perfect the skills and relationships necessary for employees to meet the needs of the job.

2.4. Factors influence employees' work engagement

According to Demerouti et al. (2001), the author of the model “ Resources- requirements at work ” (Job Demands-Resources, JD-R), each industry and job contains elements. Own risks are related to stress at work. These factors can be categorized into 2 parts: (1) Work resources and (2) Job requirements.

According to the JD-R model, the resources and requirements at work cover many aspects.

Firstly, this model includes job requirements related to the physical, psychological, social and organizational aspects of a job that require constant physical effort, psychologically or require the necessary skills, and it is related to the physiological and psychological costs.

Secondly, work resources are related to the physical, psychological, social, and organizational aspects of a job that include or combine:

- Perform functions to help accomplish work goals.
- Reduce work requirements and costs related to physiology and psychology.
- Promote the maturity, ability to learn and develop of individuals. Can include the elements of the resources of the job are: feedback, control work, the help of society. Work resources are seen as both acting as an internal motivation because they promote personal growth and both as an external motivation because they are tools to help achieve goals at work.

2.5. Previous researches of work engagement

El-Kot et al. (2010) studied job participation in a sample of male and female managers and professionals working in various organizations and industries in Egypt. Data were collected from 242 respondents, 48 percent response rate, using anonymous completion questionnaires. Participation is assessed by three scales developed by Schaufeli (2004) vigor, dedication, and absorption. The premise includes demographic characteristics and job situation as well as measures that need achievement and workaholic behavior; the consequences include measures of job satisfaction and psychology. The results show that both a need for achievement and a workaholic work behavior are found to predict all three measures of participation. Second, participation, especially dedication, predicts different job outcomes (for example, job satisfaction, intention to quit job). The study has certain limitations because causality cannot be solved because data is collected at a time. Longitudinal studies are needed to determine the impact of life experiences at work on participation. Accordingly, organizations can increase their level of job participation by creating supportive work experiences (e.g. control, reward and recognition) that are consistent with human resource management practices (HRM) effective.

Figure 1: Effectors creating employees' satisfaction

(Source: SOURCE El-Kot et al, 2010)

Low work engagement can contribute to reduced performance. Therefore, the evaluation, promotion and maintenance of participation in the work is the concern of many organizations. De Beer et al. (2016) assessed systematically with a meta-analysis to evaluate evidence of the effectiveness of work-related interventions using the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES). Studies containing relevant quantitative data have undergone random meta effect analyzes. Results were assessed for uniformity, systematic sampling error, publishing bias, and quality. Twenty studies met inclusion criteria and were categorized into four types of interventions: (i) individual resource building; (ii) build employment resources; (iii) leadership training; and (iv) health promotion. Moderator analyzes revealed an important outcome for the intervention style, with moderate to large effects on the group interventions. The heterogeneity between the studies was high and the success of the implementation was varied.

Figure 2. Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES)

(Source: De Beer et al. 2016)

Research by Torp et al. (2012) investigated whether work needs, personal control and social support affect the negative health measure of depression differently from positive work engagement measures and investigate whether work engagement mediates the effects of job needs and resources at the level of depression. The authors discussed the significance of using engagement as a measure of results in improving workplace health with a sample number of 605. In multivariate analysis, the need for work as well as high social control and support are significantly correlated with high levels of work engagement. Research shows that engagement mediates the effects of social control and support on depression. Encouraging businesses to improve their engagement in addition to focusing on disease prevention can be worthwhile in promoting workplace health. Promoting engagement can have a more positive organizational impact than the focus on traditional disease prevention, because participation is relevant and closely related to good performance and motivation.

Figure.3: Model of Torp et al. (2012) about work engagement

(Source: Torp et al, 2012)

According to Ten et al. (2012), a New way of working (NWW), which allows employees to choose time and place of work, is increasingly being implemented in organizational practice, but some studies have addressed the pros and cons to employee results. The authors examined the impact of NWW on work engagement and work exhaustion. Research results show that daily use of NWW is positively associated with daily work engagement and negative to daily exhaustion due to increased effective and effective communication. In addition, NWW enhances connections among peers, leading to increased daily work engagement and reduced exhaustion. However, we also found a positive relationship between NWW and burnout, because NWW increased disruption during work. The authors have carefully concluded that NWW has the potential to drive engagement.

In the study of Stan et al. (2014), the authors focused on engaging in work as an intermediate variable. Traditionally, participation in work is defined as a positive, fulfilling mind, related to the job characterized by vitality, dedication and absorption. Engaging in work is not a state of uncertain mind, but perseverance and no direct focus on a particular object, event, individual or behavior. Worker participation consists of three elements: strong, devoted and absorbing. Raising employee morale is affected by high energy level, resilience, willingness to invest effort and steadfastness in the face of problems. Dedication by the employee's enthusiastic pride in the work, the feeling of work inspiration and the overall sense of importance related to the job. Absorb a state of mind in which employees are highly focused and engrossed in their work. Participation in work and

internal motivation are similar concepts. Participation does not represent a specific driver of employee engagement, but only the strength, dedication and commitment of employees, without distinction between different sources. Participation has been linked to positive organizational outcomes related to employee behavior and has been found to be an intermediary variable that operates in the relationship between job characteristics and employees. The authors also argue that autonomy not only allows employees to demonstrate creative work practices, but also promotes their overall participation and advocacy. Autonomy allows employees to achieve work goals and respond quickly to changing work needs, and create the negative of stress factors. This has the ability to enable employees to work better with strong and devoted work. Numerous studies have confirmed that autonomy and participation in work are positively related.

Figure 4: Model of work engagement Stan et al

(Source: Stan et al, 2014)

From the point of view of coherence measurement, using direct measures of individual perceptions, including behavioral and attitudinal aspects, Mowday et al. (1979) established a scale of measure employees' sense of organization by studying: "The Measurement of Organizational Commitment". By using the definition of Organizational Commitment (OC) as the power of individual identity with the organization and active participation in the organization, Mowday and his colleagues identified three components of OC including: (i) Strongly believe in the organization, accept its goals and values, (ii) Be willing to work hard for the organization, and (iii) Strongly desire to be a member of the main function of organization. Accordingly, a 15-item survey questionnaire (OCQ) was developed by the researchers to explore the three aspects of OC and use the 07-item Likert scale. The quota for men and women is presented based on the available template. Satisfactory test reliability and internal consistency reliability were found, based on a series of studies among 2563 employees in nine different organizations.

The results of the study have shown the importance of OCQ in measuring the intention to stay and organize (considered as one of the three components of OC) in each study. Many other studies have shown that OCQ has given similar results when it measures how long employees are expected to stay in the organization. Accordingly, employees with interest and career orientation are considered to have a higher level of cohesion in the organization. Correlations between OC and the JDI (Job Descriptive Index) scale were also found. The strongest relationships are often found between commitment and job satisfaction.

Stefan Gaertner (1999) clarified the structure of job-related factors and OC with research: "Structural determinants of Job satisfaction and Organizational commitment in turnover model". With data including 7,040 samples (mainly office workers, 49% of which are male), taken from 9 empirical studies, the author used

LISREL 8.3 to conduct analysis of Meta-Analytical Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The author has used 10 elements (Salary; Opportunity for promotion; Fair distribution; Colleague support; Superior support; Workload; Conflict; No transparency; Autonomy) ; Habits) to measure the extent and how these elements influence job satisfaction and engagement. The research results show that all 10 components have a direct relationship with job satisfaction but only 3 components (promotion opportunities; fair distribution; support of superiors) are related directly with engagement.

Figure 5: Relationship of Structural Determinants and Organizational Commitment/Job Satisfaction

(Source: Gaertner , 1999)

There are many definitions of work engagement for businesses in the field of human resource management. From 2000 to the present, the number of research, publications and articles related to the participation of the work, or the engagement of employees has skyrocketed both in quantity and quality. From the first academic paper on workplace engagement published by William Kahn (1990) in the Management Academy Magazine, the changes in the world of work, the positive psychological movement was announced and published by a group of academics working with Martin Seligman, then president of the American Psychological Association, that promoted the development of "work engagement " issues.

Engagement refers to participation, commitment, passion, enthusiasm, uptake, focused effort and energy. Work engagement first appears in business, despite its roots terminology is not entirely clear, it was first used in the 1990s by Gallup Foundation (1990)

According to Maslach and Leiter (1997) work engagement is basically formed in aspects including emotional attachment to the organization and commitment to continued (i.e. desire to stay with the organization) and off-role behaviors (i.e. arbitrary behavior that promotes the effective functioning of the organization). Conceptually in this way, employee engagement constitutes a mix of the two existing psychological concepts. As a result, it seems most consulting firms are bringing new entrants into the old commitment and bottle the complementary

role. The employees involved have put a lot of effort into the work because they sympathize with it. Engagement is also said to produce positive results, both at the individual level (personal growth and development) as well as the organizational level (quality of performance). In contrast to those who are exhausted, the employees involved consciously connect energy and efficiency with their work; instead of stress and demanding they see their work as challenging. Accordingly, engagement is characterized by energy, participation and efficiency, forming the direct opposites of three dimensions of exhaustion - exhaustion, cynicism and reduced achievement. In this view, engagement and exhaustion are inherently linked and can therefore be assessed by the same method. In addition, engagement is considered to be an independent, distinct concept that is negatively related to burnout. It is defined in its true sense as a group of positive, fulfilling, work-related states, characterized by vitality, dedication and absorption. Work engagement is characterized by a high level of energy and resilience while working, a willingness to invest effort in another job, and perseverance even when it is difficult. Consciousness refers to being strongly involved in one's work, and experiencing feelings of meaning, enthusiasm, inspiration, pride and challenge. Finally, absorption is characterized by complete concentration and happiness immersed in one's work, through which time passes quickly and hard with separation from work as Schaufeli (2012).

Kahn (1990) argues that employees who engage in work will devote their entire mind, knowledge, and physical ability to the task, but this definition may be confused with other factors such as organizational behavior or satisfied / dissatisfied at work. In order to better understand the different levels of individuals attached to their roles, Kahn (1990) examined a number of principles. The terms Kahn (1990) use to describe these calibrations are 'personal participation' and 'personal disengagement', which refer to the behaviors of people they include or ignore individual roles while performing their job roles. These terms developed by Kahn (1990) integrate previous ideas taken from motivational theories that people need to express and self-control in work life is obvious.

According to Britt (1999; 2003), the definition of work coherence is personal responsibility and a commitment to fulfill and focus on getting work done.

Maslach and Leiter (1997) assume that work engagement is the complete opposite of exhaustion, so work cohesion includes: energy, commitment, and personal achievement. Schaufeli et al (2002) in their new research model suggest that work cohesion is defined as a state of persistence, positivity, and motivation for accomplishment. Ulrich (2007) values employees' contribution in business because when businesses try to create more outputs, businesses have to find ways to engage employees both mentally and mentally to increase labor productivity.

Various definitions of job linkage are also provided in study of Macey and Schneider (2008). Accordingly, work engagement is the energy level of a user to work effectively and efficiently. However, according to Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), work engagement is considered as a state of oscillation in themselves, employees who are attached to the job, but who may have holidays and non-employment status are the same for all days. It is important for organizations to recognize employees who are truly psychologically connected at work (employees who are truly engaged with the job) because they are always ready and able to devote themselves to the mind. In their role, these employees are very motivated and always work towards high quality work standards Bakker & Leiter (2010).

Work engagement is defined as a positive, satisfying, work-related mental state characterized by attributes of dedication and enthusiasm Schaufeli and Bakker, (2010). Accordingly, different from the concept of "employee engagement" in the direction of engagement with the organization, work engagement involves the mental states expressed in the verbal thinking and actions of employees to work: as devoted to work, focused on work, passionate about work, worked hard and energetic. The cohesion mentioned in this concept refers to the state of awareness and continuity of action and does not focus on any object, individual or event or behavior. Bakker (2009) gives three factors that measure work cohesion: energetic: energetic and willing to work hard even when

facing difficulties; dedicating factors: devoting your mind to work, feeling work with enthusiasm, always being inspired, proud of the job; Passion factor: be completely focused on your work and happy to spend all your time at work.

Although the aforementioned sample may feel tired after a long day at work, they consider it a pleasant state, which is well worth the positive results at work. Employees who are attached to work are not workaholics, they also enjoy other activities of life outside of work, so for those who are engaged with work, working is joyful (Gorgievski, Bakker & Schaufeli, 2010).

3. Vietnamese studies on employees work engagement

- In Vietnam, research of Pham Duy Khanh and Tran Dinh Long (2015) studied factors affecting employee's engagement with businesses at Military Petroleum Corporation. The research model in the article uses Cronbach's Alpha reliability assessment method and EFA discovery factor analysis used to screen out the factors that meet the requirements. The results of the regression model estimation show that "Employee evaluation", "Job identification", "Training, remuneration and compensation", "Recruitment" are important factors that have a positive impact on the engagement of employee with businesses.

- Ha Nam Khanh Giao and Nguyen Dang Huyen Tran (2017) in "Industry and Trade Magazine" studied the factors affecting employee engagement with Ho Chi Minh Banking University, by surveying 174 employees using Cronbachs alpha, EFA and multiple regression analysis. The results showed a model of 05 factors that have a positive impact on employee engagement, in descending order: Nature of work, Colleague relations, School reputation, Salaries and benefits, the support from the superior. On that basis, the author proposes administrative solutions to the board of directors and the heads of units to increase employee engagement.

- The study "Assessing organizational awareness and job satisfaction in the Vietnamese context" by Tran Kim Dung and Abraham (2005) explored the relationship between job satisfaction and sense of attachment. Based on a research sample of 396 full-time employees in Ho Chi Minh City, the author used a network model, through 3 components of consciousness associated with the organization and 5 aspects of public satisfaction. Research shows that employees work hard and are proud of their workplace because they like the job and have a good relationship at work.

- In addition, many domestic authors have studied the factors that affect employee's long-term engagement with all types of businesses. In the field of services, author Nguyen Chi Cong (2011) with the study "Solutions to create long-term cohesion of employees with enterprises in VNPT member units", used the explore factor analysis method EFA and multivariate regression analysis to analyze factors that affects employee engagement. The results of the analysis show that significant positive impact factors on employee long-term engagement include job satisfaction and family influence. At the same time, the author also pointed out that there is a difference in the intention of long-term association with businesses between different education and income groups. Among those with higher education and postgraduate, the level of engagement with businesses in terms of intention is lower than those with lower education. And those with an income of five million or more have a higher degree of engagement with businesses than those with lower incomes.

- Tran Van Tuan, (2018) applied the scale of reward and recognition, organizational fairness, organizational support awareness, job characteristics, work engagement and organizational citizenship M. (2006) in real life conditions at some Non-life Insurance Companies in Ho Chi Minh City. Qualitative research was conducted by the author to adjust and supplement the theory and research scale. Quantitative research conducted with a sample of 283 employees with 1 year of working experience or more working full-time in Ho Chi Minh City. Analysis results show that Organizational Justice In terms of work engagement, the Rewards and Recognition factors are considered as two separate factors with different levels of impact on work engagement.

3. Conclusion

Regarding physical value, FDI companies in Bac Ninh need to improve working conditions with measures such as creating landscapes and working environment close to nature, inspiring work. Companies can also improve the quality of lunch and the quality of transportation to mid-level managers. Companies also need to be equipped with simple work tools, such as managers who need to be equipped with laptops to facilitate their work, have phone costs and special protective clothing to ensure safety. In the case of enterprises operating in the field of industry, chemicals. In addition, companies can also provide health insurance for middle managers and their relatives, giving them peace of mind to work engagement. In addition, companies need to define and set clear goals, pay performance-based payroll (following KPI) to help middle managers see the salary they are entitled to. Companies also have to regularly review the industry average wage and other FDI enterprises correlating with the workload to be able to adjust the salary accordingly. The performance of mid-level managers also needs to be linked to the performance of their subordinate units and must be appropriately designed to enable managers to achieve their full potential abilities as well as balance the pressure of work and life.

About personnel policies, the author agrees with Mohamad (2017) that employees are often required to engage in activities designed to promote an enhanced work environment. In line with company policy, regular operations increase employee cohesion. To increase work engagement, companies often have an annual event policy, such as vacation time, central dinner, off-site events and bonuses. Promoting the cultural competence of the entire organization means to improve the competence of employees. Many companies encourage work engagement by offering non-financial rewards or even changing employees every day. Staff involvement is related to the psychological experience of those who shape their work processes and behaviors. Improving work engagement is a multidimensional process, best achieved through the increased daily work engagement of employees' emotions, physical and cognitive. The company's employee engagement policy needs deals with providing a safe working environment for all employees. Organizational leaders are responsible for providing the needs of their employees by providing appropriate training and building a meaningful work environment. In turn, employees are responsible for providing a meaningful contribution to the organization. According to studies conducted by Gallup Consulting and SHRM, which shows organizations with high staff participation are more profitable than organizations without employees attached to the job.

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